

The Smart Islands method for defining energy planning scenarios on islands

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Abstract

Islands represent areas where it is possible to have a clear overview of resources and needs over a large number of sectors. Because of this, the developed energy planning scenarios on the islands should reflect the possibility of meeting local needs with available resources of a wide range of sectors. This is often not the case in the current studies that analyse only a limited number of sectors. The developed method automatically combines needs and resources based on the quantitative indicators and generates energy planning scenarios with precisely defined types and the capacities of required technologies. The results show that the Smart Islands method provides 7 energy planning scenarios for Krk island with different technology mixes. The case study for Vis island is considered for cases with and without electrical interconnection. When the interconnection is not considered, the method suggests a 5.42 MWh battery system for maintaining grid stability. The results indicate that the Smart Islands method can be applied to islands with different characteristics as well as suggest optimal energy planning scenarios while meeting needs with local resources.

Keywords: *Energy planning, Smart Islands method, Renewable energy sources, RenewIslands, Energy system modelling, Smart energy systems*

1. Introduction

Energy planning of islands is becoming increasingly important as the European Union (EU) increases its effort to tackle climate change. The idea that islands can be “living labs” for the new technology and projects laid the foundations for islands to take the leading role in the energy transition towards a clean and sustainable environment. Islands are considered to be unique areas because of many disadvantages they are exposed to such as a weak electrical grid connection, higher fuel prices, overall weaker infrastructure etc. On the other hand, the islands are unique areas because they offer a possibility to have a clearer overview of needs and resources available and often have better solar and wind potential than on the mainland. The implementation of the new technology on unique locations such as islands opens the possibility for replication of solutions achieved on the islands in the mainland areas. The role of islands and objectives for the successful process of the energy transition on the islands are framed within the two documents by the EU, the Smart Islands Initiative [1] and the Clean Energy for EU Islands [2].

RenewIslands method presented in [3] focused on meeting island needs by using local resources and presenting the qualitative framework for energy experts for defining energy planning scenarios. RenewIslands method was applied to numerous case studies including S. Vicente [4] where the authors concluded that it is possible to achieve 72% of generation from RES. The authors at [5] used RenewIslands for generating energy planning scenarios and EnergyPLAN for modelling the interconnection and the demand response (DR) between different islands. The method for defining energy planning scenarios for islands was presented in [6], however, this method is also based on the qualitative RenewIslands method and defines one energy planning scenario depending on the objective function of the problem.

Other studies use different approaches for defining energy planning scenarios without a clear indication of why a particular scenario was modelled. A case for 100% renewable island of Wang-An modelled in EnergyPLAN was presented in [7] where the authors used electricity, thermal and transport demand while the RES potential was assessed based on geographical conditions of the island. A RES scenario for the renewable island of Ustica with 324.9 MWh renewable generation was presented in [8], however, it remained unclear why particular technologies were chosen for simulated scenario. Another example of energy transition scenario for islands in the Philippines was presented in [9] where the authors considered only scenarios with the fossil fuel generation. The presented studies proposed different energy planning scenarios for the energy transition of islands, however, it is not clear how did the authors choose the energy planning scenarios that were analysed. It is clear that there is a lack of such approaches that consider islands' needs and resources for devising energy planning scenarios.

The need for quantifying the impact of cross-sector integration is highly recognized by the various authors that analysed many different scenarios and solutions. The possibility for completely renewable Canary Islands was presented in [10] where the authors suggested that integration of transportation and heating sector with electric power system should be implemented. Islands without electrical interconnection were studied in [11] on the case of the Faroe Islands and the authors proposed a combination of wind and hydrogen technology for the development of sustainable energy systems. Lund et al. [12] elaborated on a holistic approach for achieving a cross-sectoral smart energy system that provides flexibility through several different sectors such as heating, synthetic fuels production and transport. Similarly, the study at [13] presented four possibilities for interconnecting electricity generation and transport systems that resulted in a 50% possibility increase for integration of variable RES. The energy planning tool PLEXOS was used in [14] where the authors concluded that it is possible to

reduce oil imports by 46% on Caribbean Islands when integrating different sectors, namely the cooling, water and transport sector with the electricity sector. The possibility for integration of solar concentrated power and desalination on Dongsha island was presented in [15] where the authors conclude that smart integration of these technologies can result in a 100% renewable island. However, it is not clear how the proposed cross-sectoral solutions for flexibility increase reflect the islands' needs and available resources.

Methods for comparisons of different technologies as well as energy storage sizing were also extensively investigated. A recent study [16] provided a review of the latest energy storage and demand response technologies, as well as underlined the importance of sector integration for increasing the flexibility on the islands. A review of methods for microgrid planning was provided in [17] where the authors elaborate on different methods for microgrid power generation planning. However, the study did not consider a broader approach where many sectors would be included. Chen et al [18] concluded that the optimal energy storage size for considered microgrid in island mode is 1.4 MWh, but did not consider possibilities for sector integration for providing additional flexibility that could lower the needs for flexibility from the energy storage system (ESS) and result with the lower optimal value of ESS. Optimal planning of reserve and power generation of microgrids was presented in [19] where the authors compare the microgrid with ESS and microgrid with the DR but without ESS. The authors concluded that the microgrid with ESS has a 31.16% lower energy cost. The study [20] showed that citizens' participation in the demand response management systems leads to energy cost reduction for the users. Another study [21] concluded that the breakpoint incentive for the demand response is 23% of the day-ahead electricity market price, however without specifying how is the level of flexibility determined. The authors in [22] propose a STEEP approach for the assessment of microgrid failure factors in local communities. The bi-level optimization

approach for microgrid planning and operation is presented in [23] where the authors conclude that it is possible to achieve 84.44% savings in comparison to the base case scenario when the presented method is applied. However, these studies focused only on specific sector without examining the impact of sector coupling.

The study in [24] examined the impact of energy policy on dynamics of the energy transition for the case study of Reunion Island where the authors concluded that the current energy policy in France is slowing down the energy transition on Reunion Island.

Energy planning studies on the regional and national level often consider a limited number of sectors without the objective of meeting the needs of an area with its resources. For example, the study [25] considered coupling of heating and power sector and the authors in [26] considered integration of residential heating and transport sector. The study [27] expanded the approach and considered waste and geothermal resources, however, the capacity optimization was not performed and arbitrary scenarios were considered. The possibility to quantify the flexibility would be especially interesting for regional planning, especially for spatially distributed planning as in [28]. Since the islands have a clearer overview of available needs and resources than the areas on the mainland, the solutions and methods developed on the islands can contribute to resolving issues on the mainland.

The method developed in this paper answers the following research questions derived from the analyzed literature:

- How to define the method for defining the exact type and quantity of required technologies for meeting islands' needs with its resources based on quantitative indicators?
- How to automatize the process of defining energy planning scenarios that match islands' needs and resources?

- How to consider electricity, heating, cooling, transport, water, waste and wastewater sectors in such a method?
- How to quantify the available flexibility of energy scenarios obtained with such a method?

The hypothesis of this study is that by using the new method for calculation of energy planning scenarios on islands (Smart Islands method) it can be shown that the transformation of energy systems on islands to systems that can satisfy all their energy demand from renewable energy sources is possible with a precisely defined amount and type of required technology.

Moreover, the research objectives of this study are as follows:

- Automatization of RenewIslands method implemented in Python programming language
- A novel method for defining the type and quantity of required technology
- A development of case studies for Krk and Vis islands that includes electricity, heating, cooling, transport, water, waste and wastewater sector
- Statistical analysis of energy planning scenarios by using Monte Carlo simulation for the two cases of uncertainty

The paper is organized in the following structure: The introduction is given in the first section of the study, the second section of the paper presents the Smart Islands method developed within this study. The case study on which the method has been applied is presented in the third section, while the fourth section presents the results of the study. The fifth section presents the discussion and the final section presents the conclusions of the study.

2. Material and Methods

The Smart Islands method developed in this study is a tool that enables islands' planners to automatically calculate the quantity and type of technology required for meeting islands' needs with resources. The method considers electricity, heating, cooling, transport, water, waste and wastewater sector and is implemented in the programming language Python. The method is based on the RenewIslands method developed by Duić in [3]. There are two main parts of the method that will be further explained in the paper:

- (1) Calculate possible types of technologies that can meet islands' needs with resources by considering the input indicators (chapter 2.1)
- (2) Perform a capacity optimization by considering only technologies calculated from the first part and repeat the optimization procedure for all possible electricity production combinations (chapter 2.2)

The main advantage of the method is that it automates the process from mapping to generating energy planning scenarios. This means that one can in few seconds generate energy planning scenarios that meet islands' needs with resources once the input data is defined.

It should be noted that, although the method considers many operation parameters (e.g. load factor, variability factor), the method itself is not intended to analyse the operation of the system. It is recommended that the scenarios are further analysed with energy planning tools (e.g. EnergyPLAN [29], H2RES [30], Homer [31]). Moreover, if one would want to assess the possibilities for practical implementations of the scenarios, tools for electric power system analysis should be included in the analysis as well (e.g., NEPLAN [32], DigSILENT [33], PSS/E [34]). The additional analyses with mentioned tools may indicate the need to change the capacities or increase investments in the infrastructure because of special operating conditions of the energy system that may occur (e.g. peak demand that lasts for an extended period, voltage problems may occur in the distribution grids etc.).

The scenarios obtained with the Smart Islands method provide an insight into the possibilities for matching needs with resources at the lowest investment cost. This information is valuable to the decision-makers and policymakers and the scenarios should primarily be used for these purposes. It is also suggested that the scenarios are used as input data for previously mentioned energy planning tools, or, in other words, that the Smart Islands method is used as the pre-processing step for the energy planning tools.

Input data for the Smart islands method are indicators presented in [35] that are divided into four areas A_1 to A_4 and summarized in Appendix A. These areas cover islands' needs, resources, infrastructure and water resources for mentioned sectors. The input data can be defined with more indicators (e.g. biomass potential), however, the intent was to achieve an adequate trade-off between the complexity of input indicators and the quality of the results. The Smart Islands method is visually presented in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 presents an outline of the method with every step and actors included, while Figure 2 presents what input data is needed for different technology selection.

Figure 1. Smart Islands method outline diagram – the blue boxes represent the first part of the method (matching islands’ needs with resources), the green boxes present the optimization part of the method, while input data is given in the orange box

Figure 2. Smart Islands method for defining energy planning scenarios

2.1. Automated RenewIslands method

The first step of the Smart Islands method is to automatize the RenewIslands method. The RenewIslands is a qualitative method that is used for energy planning of the islands. A novel approach for the automatization of the RenewIslands method is implemented in the Python programming language in the scripts *Modulemethod.py* and *AuthRenewIslands.py*. The input indicators are loaded in the Python script *Modulemethod.py* where the classes for energy carriers, production technologies, storage technologies and flow integration are defined together with the corresponding functions. *AuthRenewIslands.py* is the script that is used for the calculation of scenarios that are defined with several lists as outputs. The software architecture for defining energy planning scenarios by using automatized RenewIslands is presented in Figure 3. The logic implemented in the programming code is available in Appendix B.

Figure 3. Programming architecture for automatization of RenewIslands method – main output of this part of Smart Islands method is to obtain all possible technologies that match islands’ needs with resources based on the input data

2.2. Optimization model

By automatizing the RenewIslands method it is possible to calculate qualitative energy planning scenarios directly from mapping data of the islands. With this contribution, the application of RenewIslands is significantly accelerated and subjected to quantitative indicators. In order to create the Smart Islands method, it is necessary to create the optimization model for calculating

the required quantity of specific technology obtained from the first part of the method. As stated in the introduction, integration of different sectors such as electricity, water, heating, transport etc. is becoming increasingly important in order to achieve sustainable systems. This is due to the fact that the increasing share of variable RES is introducing numerous uncertainties in the electric power systems which are especially highlighted on the islands which are usually characterized by low inertia. By adjusting the operation of other systems such as water or heating system it is possible to improve conditions in the electric power grid and increase the possibility for RES integration. As maintaining the stability of an electric power system is crucial for achieving high RES systems, the optimization model presented in this study is oriented towards energy planning scenarios with different combinations of electricity generation units. This means that the method repeats the optimization procedure until all possible electricity production technologies obtained from the first part of the method are iterated. A complete flow diagram for defining possible energy planning scenarios for islands is provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Flow diagram for Smart islands method implementation

2.2.1. Objective function and variables

The objective of the optimization problem is to minimize the specific investment cost of technology for a given energy planning scenario. Although various objectives can be implemented such as minimizing energy dependence of the island or maximizing self-sustainability as elaborated in the introduction, this methods' objective is to minimize the specific investment cost of derived energy planning scenarios on islands. A similar approach can be found in [6] or [36]. The considered assumption is that the operation and maintenance cost would further underline solar and wind as the most affordable technologies. Additionally,

the operation cost depends on the type of technology that is installed (e.g. biomass generator). The Monte Carlo analysis is used to analyse the uncertainty of the cost. Considered uncertainty is +/- 10% from the expected specific cost and it is assumed that such a large uncertainty range is sufficient to observe the results for wide errors in the investment cost of the technologies. The overall objective of the method is to, first, determine all possible technologies for consideration concerning the islands' needs and resources and then calculate all possible energy planning scenarios with a precisely sized quantity of each technology, represented with variables \mathbf{x} of the problem. In this sense, let linear programming optimization problem be defined as equation (1):

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in S} \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

$$S = \{ \mathbf{x} | \mathbf{A}^{in} \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}^{in}, \mathbf{A}^{eq} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}^{eq}, \mathbf{x} \geq 0 \}$$

Where S is a convex set, $\mathbf{A}^{in} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times n}$ is inequality equation matrix, $\mathbf{A}^{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times n}$ is equality equation matrix, $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is specific investment cost vector, $\mathbf{b}^{in} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is inequality vector, $\mathbf{b}^{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^q$ is equality vector and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are variables of the problem. Sets of variables of the problem are defined with Table 1, each of them having assigned cost. Different relations between the variables are described with equality and inequality constraints. The variables of the problem are considered to be quantitative values of installed electrical power generation of a particular technology, the capacity of storage, thermal generation etc. The specific investment cost vector of different technologies is obtained from data available in the literature [27]–[38]. The product of variable representing the quantity of a specific technology and assigned specific investment cost is implemented with function *calculate_sum* that contains additional check-ups by comparing the size of the list of technologies and list of cost.

After executing function *calculate_new_techs* and defining new lists of different technologies, the model defines variables for the optimization problem. This is implemented with series of *for* loops where one variable is generated for every element of each list of technologies that are generated with function *calculate_new_techs*. The variables in the presented optimization problem represent the required quantity of specific technology. Complete list of variable sets is provided in Table 1, where $X_{eg} = \{x_{eg,1}, \dots, x_{eg,5}\}$, $X_{es} = \{x_{es,1}, \dots, x_{es,4}\}$, $X_{tg} = \{x_{tg,1}, \dots, x_{tg,4}\}$, $X_{cg} = \{x_{cg,1}, \dots, x_{cg,3}\}$, $X_{ts} = \{x_{ts,1}, x_{ts,2}\}$, $X_{tt} = \{x_{tt,1}, \dots, x_{tt,3}\}$, $X_{tts} = \{x_{tts,1}, x_{tts,2}\}$, $X_{wg} = \{x_{wg,1}, \dots, x_{wg,3}\}$, $X_{wt} = \{x_{wt,1}\}$, $X_{wwt} = \{x_{wwt,1}\}$, $X_{ws} = \{x_{ws,1}, \dots, x_{ws,3}\}$. Thus, total number of possible variables is equal to 31. Each of these variables has corresponding cost assigned with vector \mathbf{c}^T .

Table 1. List of variables of Smart islands method

Variables	Mark	Unit	Implementation in programming code
Electricity generation	$x_{eg,i}$	MW	gen
Electricity storage	$x_{es,i}$	MWh	stor
Thermal generation	$x_{tg,i}$	MW	th_prod
Cooling generation	$x_{cg,i}$	MW	cold_prod
Thermal storage	$x_{ts,i}$	MWh	th_stor
Transport technology	$x_{tt,i}$	MW	transp_tech
Transport storage	$x_{tts,i}$	MWh	transp_stor
Water supply technology	$x_{wg,i}$	MW	water_tech
Waste treatment technology	$x_{wt,i}$	MW	waste_tech
Wastewater treatment technology	$x_{wwt,i}$	MW	ww_tech
Water, waste and wastewater storage	$x_{ws,i}$	tonne (waste)	www_stor
		m ³ (else)	

The objective function \mathcal{F} of the observed linear optimization problem can then be written as (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \min \mathcal{F} = \min & \left(\sum_{X_{eg}} x_{eg,i} \cdot c_{eg,i} + \sum_{X_{es}} x_{es,i} \cdot c_{es,i} + \sum_{X_{tg}} x_{tg,i} \cdot c_{tg,i} + \sum_{X_{cg}} x_{cg,i} \cdot \right. \\ & c_{cg,i} + \sum_{X_{ts}} x_{ts,i} \cdot c_{ts,i} + \sum_{X_{tt}} x_{tt,i} \cdot c_{tt,i} + \sum_{X_{tts}} x_{tts,i} \cdot c_{tts,i} + \sum_{X_{wg}} x_{wg,i} \cdot \\ & \left. c_{wg,i} + \sum_{X_{wt}} x_{wt,i} \cdot c_{wt,i} + \sum_{X_{wwt}} x_{wwt,i} \cdot c_{wwt,i} + \sum_{X_{ws}} x_{ws,i} \cdot c_{ws,i} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

2.2.2. Constraints

The constraints of the proposed method consist of 13 inequality constraints and 1 equality constraint represented with equations (3) – (16) with bounding condition $\mathbf{x} \geq 0$ for all variables.

The proposed Smart Islands method accounts for islands' resources and matches them with islands' needs. Therefore, it is required that the generation of specific technology does not exceed the potentials available on the island. It is also required that islands use technologies for which there is more available potential. This is achieved by loading the list of potentials mapped with the input indicators and setting following constraints (3) and (4) where $E_{\text{pot}} = \{ E_{\text{pot},1}, \dots, E_{\text{pot},5} \}$ represents the potential of each resource:

$$x_{eg,i} \leq E_{\text{pot},i} \quad (3)$$

$$x_{eg,i} \geq x_{eg,j} \cdot \frac{E_{\text{pot},i}}{E_{\text{pot},j}} \quad (4)$$

The constraints regarding minimal electricity, heating and cooling generation are described with equations (5) – (7). The maximum electricity generation capacities must be sufficient to satisfy the maximum electricity load (P_{max}). The Smart Island method sets a 20% higher requirement for generation capacity in order to secure that there will be enough amount of renewable power generation in case of increased demand. The equation also accounts for electricity production

from Waste-to-Energy plants (WtE) and wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) if available. The values for heating production in the case of cogeneration are also accounted for with defined quotients α_1 and α_2 which represent the ratio of heating power and electrical power generation. The required heating and cooling variables were set to satisfy the maximum heating and cooling load which is expressed with the equations (6) and (7). In case there are no available local resources for meeting local needs, the model will be unfeasible and the tool would return the corresponding message. However, such a scenario is unlikely as it would be difficult to find a populated island without any resources.

$$\sum_{x_{eg}} x_{eg,i} + x_{wt} + x_{wwt} \geq 1.2P_{max} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{x_{tg}} x_{tg,i} + \alpha_1 x_{wt} + \alpha_2 x_{wwt} \geq L_h \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{x_{cg}} x_{cg,i} \geq L_c \quad (7)$$

Maximum required power in the transport sector is determined with the quotient of transport demand divided by the load factor available from input indicators. The assumption for the transport sector is that increase in electricity load described with the load factor is enough precise measurement for the increase of the transport sector as well. This assumption can be justified by the fact that the number of residents of the island increases six times during the summer months which corresponds to the increase in electricity consumption [44]. Additionally, a conversion factor β is defined for each specific type of fuel used in the transportation system since the transport demand in input indicators is the energy equivalent for petrol and diesel. This is given with the constraint (8).

$$\beta \sum_{i=1}^n x_{tt,i} \geq \frac{D_t}{m} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where } \beta = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for biofuels} \\ 2, & \text{for hydrogen} \\ 3, & \text{for electricity} \end{cases}$$

High amounts of variable RES such as solar and wind generation are the cause of many uncertainties in the electric power system. In order to overcome periods of a substantial change of generated power, the electric power system has to have enough units that can provide a reserve to the system. The reserve can be provided through the interconnection if the island is connected to the mainland, and by using batteries, conventional generators or the DR. For conventional systems without variable RES the minimum required amount of reserve is well investigated. Penetration of variable RES imposes new requirements for available reserve as in [45]. The reserve requirements are determined with factors $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \Gamma_3 \in [0,1]$, and are specific for different case studies. The reserve constraint is defined with equation (9) where I represents the available interconnection capacity.

$$\Gamma_1 \cdot P_{max} + \Gamma_2 \cdot x_{eg,wind} + \Gamma_3 \cdot x_{eg,solar} \leq I + DR + x_{eg,biomass} + x_{eg,geothermal} + \sum_{x_{es}} x_{es,i} \quad (9)$$

For case hydrogen or biofuels are used for transport there is a requirement for transport storage. The required size of storage should be sufficient to satisfy a share of transport demand defined with factor β_1 . This is given with the constraint (10)

$$x_{tts,i} \geq \beta_1 \cdot D_t \quad (10)$$

In case there is a need for heating and cooling storage, their values are defined with equation (11). A condition set for heating and cooling demand is that they are able to cover a share of heating or cooling demand defined with coefficients α_3 and α_4 .

$$x_{ts,i} \geq \begin{cases} \alpha_3 D_h, & i = 1 \\ \alpha_4 D_c, & i = 2 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

In case that the desalination plant is chosen as a water technology, its power required for operation is calculated using the available load factor. Similarly to the transport sector, it is assumed that the water demand can be approximated with the load factor as well. The specific power consumption of desalination was taken as in [46] and interpreted with coefficient α_5 . The described constraint is given with equation (12).

$$x_{wg,des} \geq \alpha_5 \frac{D_w}{m} \quad (12)$$

If the waste produced on the island is not exported, but the method rather suggests that it should be treated on the island with the WtE, the constraint for the power of such plant is presented with an equation according to specifications taken from [47] and represented with coefficient α_6 . The rated power must be equal to or less than the available yearly amount of waste (13).

$$x_{wt,i} \geq \alpha_6 G_w \quad (13)$$

If the WWTP is proposed, the waste heat produced for the wastewater treatment process can be used for heating. The specifications of wastewater treatment plant are taken from [48] which is represented with coefficient α_7 and the constraint for heat production is given with constraint (14):

$$x_{wwt,i} \geq \alpha_7 G_{ww} \quad (14)$$

Waste, wastewater and water tanks are used in case other technologies are not suitable. Their value is based on coefficient α_8 that is opposite proportional to the number of times the tank is being emptied or filled during the year. The tanks have to have enough volume to ensure the entire demand is met with taking into account the number of times the tanks are being emptied/filled (15).

$$x_{ws,i} \geq \begin{cases} \alpha_8 D_w, & i = 1 \\ \alpha_8 G_w, & i = 2 \\ \alpha_8 G_{ww}, & i = 3 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The DR is achieved through the integration of different sectors. The proposed method allows different sectors integration if there is telecommunication infrastructure available on analysed islands. Factor k is introduced in order to quantify the share of power that can participate in the DR for a particular plant. Therefore, if available, the DR constraint is defined with equation (16):

$$DR = k_{des} \cdot x_{wg,des} + k_{WtE} \cdot x_{et,WtE} + k_{tt} \cdot x_{tt,el} + k_{ts} \cdot x_{ts} \quad (16)$$

2.3. Uncertainty management

The results of the method are dependent on the quality of input data. Thus, it is necessary to conduct the sensitivity analysis when the input data is subjugated to the realistic uncertainty ranges. This study uses the Monte Carlo experiments for the probabilistic assessment of the impact of the uncertain parameters, similarly as in [49]. The uncertain input data can be divided into two main categories. The first category is related to the technical input parameters that describe islands needs and resources, while the second input data category is related to the

specific investment cost of the particular technology. The uncertainty for the first category is related primarily to the measurement uncertainties conducted for the particular island, while the uncertainty for the specific cost is related to the projections of the specific investment costs of the technologies. The study does not estimate the possible future load growth as it is considered that this aspect is covered with the Monte Carlo analysis because it is one of the uncertain input parameters. The Monte Carlo experiments are conducted in the following steps:

- Generate random input data for the experiment
- Solve the method for generated input data
- Analyse and synthesize the results after generating a large number of experiments

3. Case study

In order to test the presented method, a case study is conducted on two Croatian islands – Krk in the north part of the Adriatic Sea and Vis in the south part of the Adriatic Sea. The two islands are different in their size, population and geographic conditions which are more discussed in the next chapters for each island.

3.1. Krk island

Krk is located in the Kvarner archipelago in Croatia. Krk is the largest island out of seven islands in total in the Kvarner archipelago. The population of Krk island is 19374 which makes it the most populated island in Croatia. The electricity demand in 2016 was 139.19 GWh and is obtained through the electricity interconnection with the mainland. The electric connection with the mainland is achieved with two interconnection lines with a total capacity of 170 MVA. The heating energy demand on the Krk island was equal to 136.73 GWh, the cooling energy demand was 12.871 GWh while the transport energy demand was 68.55 GWh. Krk island has very good potential for wind energy production, as wind speed is 9.25 m/s at 10 m height, and solar energy

production, as 1.429 MWh/m². There are also two identified locations for pumped hydro plant (PHP) on Krk island. Krk island also has a very good biomass potential of 192.21 MWh/m². The capacity factor for wind, PV and biomass are 0.25, 0.15 and 0.8 respectively. A lot of investments have been made in advancing the water infrastructure on the island resulting in a centre for water control on the island as well as water connection for all residents of the island. Further improvements can be made in wastewater infrastructure although there is a mechanical treatment of wastewater on Krk island. Detailed mapping and the rest of the required input data for the Smart Islands method is presented in an extensive study in [35]. The coefficients that are used in the Smart Islands method for this case study are presented in Table 2.

3.2. Vis island

Vis island is a significantly smaller island in comparison with Krk. The population of Vis is 3637 and its surface is 89.72 km². The yearly electricity demand of Vis island was 16 GWh in 2016. The available electric interconnection is 16 MVA. The heating demand for Vis island was 12 GWh, cooling demand 2.3 GWh and transport demand was 19 GWh. Vis is characterised by high solar radiation equal to 1.555 MWh/m².

Table 2. Smart islands method coefficients value

Factor	Value	Unit	Factor	Value	Unit
α_1	1.6	-	Γ_1	0.05	-
α_2	5.68	-	Γ_2	0.3	-
α_3	0.05	-	Γ_3	0.1	-
α_4	0.1	-	β_1	0.1	-
α_5	0.00675	MW/m ³	k_{des}	0.2	-
α_6	0.000063	MW/tonne	k_{WtE}	0.2	-
α_7	0.00005	MW/m ³	k_{tt}	0.2	-
α_8	0.25	-	k_{ts}	0.0001	1/h

3.3. Monte Carlo experiments

As elaborated previously in the Method part, this study uses the Monte Carlo experiments for analysing the impacts of uncertain input parameters on the energy planning scenarios for the island of Krk. Thus, the Monte Carlo is performed outside of the Smart Islands method. In order to conduct the experiments, 200 probabilistic Monte Carlo experiments are generated for two specific cases:

- Technical input parameters are considered as the uncertain variable – the uncertainty range of input data was considered to be $\pm 5\%$ from the expected value
- Specific investment costs of the technologies are considered as the uncertain variable – the uncertainty range was considered to be $\pm 10\%$ from the expected value

These cases enabled the assessment of errors in measurements and cost predictions on the final results of the case study. It is assumed that the error of measurements is less than the possible error of cost estimation, thus the uncertainty range for the input indicators is shorter than the range for cost uncertainty.

4. Results

4.1. Krk island

The results that are generated with the Smart Islands method are presented in Table 3. The presented results show the installed capacities for each scenario. The method generates 7 possible optimal energy planning scenarios depending on which electric energy sources are used. The technology for electric energy production varies from scenario to scenario aiming to achieve electric energy self-sufficiency of the island with desired technology. Most diversified electric energy sources are achieved for scenario S7 with installed wind, PV and biomass. In the S3 scenario, a PHP is suggested as a possible solution. This is reasonable as there are

remarkable peak and off-peak periods on the Krk island, which can make PHP an effective solution.

The Smart Islands method suggests heat pumps (HP), biomass boilers and heat storage as a technology solution for heating. The dominant technology for all scenarios is HPs as the most affordable solution for heating as well as cooling. However, the method also suggests the sustainable usage of the biomass technology as there is local biomass resource present on the island as well. The method also suggests solar thermal as a possible technology for heating purposes. However, the assigned value to this technology is zero as HPs are a cheaper solution. It should be noted that these technologies are usually incentivized and the Smart Island method did not consider this possibility. However, this can be accounted for by adjusting the investment cost of the technology.

Electrification of the entire transportation system is suggested for all scenarios. The Smart Islands method also proposes the installation of a desalination plant as well as waste fill and wastewater tanks as technology for treating waste and wastewater.

Table 3. Energy planning scenario as result of Smart islands method

Energy planning scenario		S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7
Electricity	Wind [MW]	60.95	0	0	30.86	57.28	0	55.88
	PV [MW]	0	60.95	0	30.1	0	57.28	1.4
	Biomass [MW]	0	0	3.67	0	3.67	3.67	3.67
	PHP [MW]	0	0	57.29	0	0	0	0
Heating	HP [MW]	55.35	55.35	48.96	55.35	48.96	48.96	48.96
	Biomass [MW]	0	0	7.34	0	7.34	7.34	7.34
	Heat storage [MWh]	13673	13673	13673	13673	13673	13673	13673
Cooling	HP [MW]	55.35	55.35	48.96	55.35	48.96	48.96	48.96
	Electricity coolers [MW]	0	0	6.18	0	6.18	6.18	6.18
Transport	EV chargers [MW]	4.55	4.55	4.55	4.55	4.55	4.55	4.55
Water	Desalination [m ³]	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.45	4.45
Waste	Waste fill [tonne]	116507	116507	116507	116507	116507	116507	116507
Wastewater	Wastewater tanks [m ³]	1745.2	1745.2	1745.2	1745.2	1745.2	1745.2	1745.2

4.1.1. Technical input parameters uncertainty

Moreover, the results are analysed by applying Monte Carlo simulation on the technical input data. 200 probabilistic scenarios are run in order to assess the Smart Islands method performance subjugated to the uncertainty of the technical input parameters. The results are presented in Figures 5-10 as boxplots. The boxplots show mean value, interquartile ranges,

minimum and maximum values. The results do not show significant differences in comparison to the scenarios presented in Table 3. The method adjusts the quantity of all technologies as the indicators change which is expected. The results indicate that the results of the Smart Island method are robust with respect to the uncertainty of the technical input data.

Figure 5. Results of Monte Carlo analysis for electricity generation technologies

Figure 6. Results of Monte Carlo analysis for heating energy generation technologies

Figure 7. Results of Monte Carlo analysis for cooling energy generation technologies

Figure 8. Results of Monte Carlo analysis for transport energy and water technologies

Figure 9. Results of Monte Carlo analysis for waste and wastewater treatment technologies

Additionally, values for the available flexibility are presented in Figure 11 with the DR parameter. As Krk has a satisfactory telecommunication infrastructure, there is a possibility for coordination between different sectors for purpose of their integration. Based on input data, the Smart Islands method proposes three flow integrations:

- Power and transport
- Power and water
- Power to heat technology.

By coordinating the operation between these sectors, the system can provide flexibility when necessary. The values for the DR parameter in the deterministic scenarios amounted to 2.33 MW (12.5% of the average load on the island), while the values after the Monte Carlo simulations are presented in Figure 10. Presented DR values adjust according to different probabilistic scenarios.

Figure 10. Results of Monte Carlo analysis for the demand response

Figure 11 shows mean values of the quantity of technology for each scenario (represented with rhombuses) and quantities obtained from original results presented in Table 3 (represented with bar plots). It is possible to observe that there are no significant differences between these results and the results obtained after 200 probabilistic scenarios which suggest the same technologies

as in the original case. For example, the highest difference for electricity generation is achieved for S5 where the quantity of suggested installed wind power between the original case and mean value of 200 scenarios differentiated for 0.3%. These results also confirm the robustness of the proposed Smart Island method with the respect to the uncertainty of the technical input parameters.

Figure 11. Comparison between original results obtained with Smart islands and mean values of Monte Carlo simulation for electricity generation technologies

4.1.2. Technology specific cost uncertainty

Since the cost of technology changes over time, it is necessary to assess the robustness of the proposed method against the uncertainty of the specific cost. Similarly to the previous Monte Carlo experiment, 200 probabilistic scenarios are run in this case as well. The results show that no deviation from the original scenarios occurs. This result indicates that the possible deviations in the specific investment cost do not influence the type and quantity of the required technology. From this result, it can be concluded that the method is robust with respect to the uncertain technology specific investment cost.

The comparison between each scenario investment cost for the two Monte Carlo experiments was also conducted (Figure 12). Higher investment costs can be seen for scenario S3 where a PHP is proposed as a solution. As the cost of PHP is significantly higher than other technologies, the cost for this scenario is higher as well. This result demonstrates that the Smart Islands method presents all possible solutions that meet island needs with island resources with respect to the cost uncertainty. It is then upon the decision-maker to decide what would be the most suitable solution among the scenarios generated with the Smart Islands method.

Figure 12. Investment costs of each energy planning scenario for two analysed cases of uncertainty

4.2. Vis island

The results for the Vis case study are presented in Table 4. The table shows scenarios generated with the Smart Islands method for two cases of interconnection availability. The difference between the two scenarios is in the installed battery capacity. For the scenario where there is no interconnection, the installed capacity of the battery storage should be 5.42 MWh. This result indicates that the Smart Islands method can be applied to islands with different interconnection capacities.

Additionally, both scenarios suggest the installation of a 5.92 MW PV plant. This is an expected result as solar potential is the dominant resource on the island. More interestingly, the results of the Vis case study align with the current ongoing projects on Vis. Recently, a 3.5 MW PV plant was installed on the island and a battery storage system is currently under construction [50]. The capacities of the technologies differ, however that is expected as the objective of the method is suitable for local communities, while the objective and possibilities of the investors may not correlate with those of local communities. The Smart Islands method also suggests the integration of the electricity and transport sector which can provide 0.3 MW (9.4% of the average load) of flexibility for the island.

Table 4. Energy planning scenarios for Vis case study for different interconnection value

Interconnection [MW]	16	0
PV [MW]	5.92	5.92
Battery storage [MWh]	0	5.42
HP [MW]	6.85	6.85
EV chargers [MW]	1.96	1.96
Desalination [m ³]	1.13	1.13
Waste fill [tonne]	232	232
Wastewater tanks [m ³]	21.4	21.4

5. Discussion

The results of this study indicate that the proposed Smart Islands method automatically generates the energy planning scenarios for islands with respect to their local needs and resources. The results of the Monte Carlo experiment suggest that the proposed method adjusts

the technologies according to the change in the input data. The technology mix and the installed values remain robust even when the technology costs are considered to be uncertain. In addition, the Smart Islands method proposes possibilities for flow integration depending on the available telecommunication infrastructure on the island. The key finding of the results is that the proposed method automatizes the process of energy planning for the smart islands. The method precisely defines the type and quantity of technology required for meeting local needs with local resources for each analysed sector.

The study [3] presented the RenewIslands method which suggested the type of technology that can be used but without precising the quantity of each technology. The fact that the study [3] did not develop the method for quantifying the required amount of each technology resulted in the research gap where different experts could suggest different amounts of required technologies. The Smart Islands method fills the research gap and improves the RenewIslands method as it provides the experts with the exact values of each technology for different energy planning scenarios that can be analysed. The results of this study are in line with the statement from [51] as every scenario assures the secure energy supply of the island. The results underline the findings of the studies [52] and [53] that defined the smart energy concepts and the flow integration of different sectors for the increase of RES penetration. Concerning the previous studies discussing the potential DR as a result of different sector integration (e.g. [12], [13] for the power and transport sector and [54] for the power and water sector), the flexibility can be increased by interconnecting different flows if the sufficient telecommunication infrastructure is available. Furthermore, the results value the importance of the interconnection as the integration of a high amount of RES would not be possible without it. The value of the interconnection and increased flexibility as a result of strong interconnection was emphasized in [5].

This study uses the Monte Carlo experiments to determine the impact of probabilistic input data on the results and showed that the results remain robust. A similar approach was taken in [55] to determine the optimal operation and sizing of the CHP. The study [56] also applied Monte Carlo experiments for the analysis of RES and energy system demand uncertainty influence.

The findings of the study place the focus on meeting island needs with its' resources, thus enhancing the self-sustainability of the island. One could argue that the objective of meeting local needs with local resources may not be the best possible solution for designing the energy planning scenarios. The other open possibility would be to eliminate the constraints of local needs and local resources and to search only for the lowest cost solutions. This study cannot prove this statement to be false. However, at least two strong arguments can be put forward to disagree with this statement. The first argument is that islands are unique areas with very limited possibilities for the integration of RES which is why local needs and resources should be considered. The second argument is that the cost of the technologies and the fuels is significantly higher on the islands than on the mainland. Consequently, the lowest cost solution on the mainland may not be the lowest cost solution on the islands. From the observed probabilistic analysis, which showed that the installed technologies remain the same even when the error in technology cost is considered, it can be concluded that the method proposed the same solutions whether the statement is adopted or not. Hence, there is no need for further consideration of this statement.

It should be noted that the proposed Smart Islands method is limited to the technologies described in the method section. However, this limitation may be easily mitigated. Further additions of the technologies may be proposed by an expert depending on the needs of the research. If the technology parameters are defined, one can simply implement the technology module in the programming code and account for any technology.

In this study, the Smart Islands method was demonstrated in the cases of the Krk and Vis islands. The methods' features and parameters are universal for all islands which makes it easy to generalize the method. The results of the method are useful for different decision-makers as national and local governments or investors in renewable energy. The Smart Islands method enables them to observe the possibilities for meeting the islands' needs with available resources at the lowest investment cost. In order to analyse the operation of the obtained scenarios, the tools for energy planning should be used. In this sense, the Smart Islands method can serve as a pre-processing method for the simulation of energy system operation and contribute the energy planning experts in the mapping of needs and resources of the island.

The proposed Smart Islands method contributes to the overall understanding of the smart energy system and provides the framework for testing the smart systems on the islands. The method will be further developed as new technologies will emerge with the overall objective of providing useful information for islands on the possibilities of meeting their own needs with local resources.

6. Conclusion

This study presents a novel Smart Islands method for energy planning of islands. The method generates energy planning scenarios based on the input data obtained from islands' mapping. The objective of the method is to propose optimal energy planning scenarios in order to meet the islands' needs by using local resources. Following contributions can be derived from the presented results:

- The results showed that, in addition to defining the type of technology, the Smart Islands method defines the precise quantity of each technology for each scenario. In the

presented case study, the Smart Islands method generated 7 renewable scenarios for Krk island for 7 different sectors

- The results showed that integration of power, heating, transport and water flows resulted in the possibility for the DR of 2.71 MW for Krk island and 0.3 MW for Vis island. This value of the DR represents the available flexibility of the system which leads to the conclusion that the Smart Island quantifies the flexibility of the system
- The results for the Vis case study showed that a 5.42 MWh battery is suggested to be installed for the scenario without the interconnection. This indicates that the method can be applied to islands regardless of their electrical interconnection.
- The Smart Islands method accelerates the process of energy planning of islands because it automatizes the design process of energy scenarios
- The results of 200 probabilistic Monte Carlo experiments for the Krk island indicated that the results of the Smart Islands method were robust under the technical input parameters uncertainty and technology-specific cost uncertainty

Future work of this research will be directed in investigating the possibilities for extending the application of the presented method to mainland areas, especially rural ones with similar characteristics to islands. Moreover, with the development of new technologies in the renewable energy sector, the method will be updated and the impacts of the new technology will be assessed.

Nomenclature

X_{eg}, x_{eg}, c_{eg}	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the electricity generation technologies
X_{es}, x_{es}, c_{es}	Set, variables [MWh] and specific investment costs [M€/MWh] for the electricity storage technologies
X_{tg}, x_{tg}, c_{tg}	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the thermal generation
$X_{cg}, x_{cg,i}, c_{cg,i}$	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the cooling generation
$X_{ts}, x_{ts,i}, c_{ts,i}$	Set, variables [MWh] and specific investment costs [M€/MWh] for the thermal storage
$X_{tt}, x_{tt,i}, c_{tt,i}$	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the transport technology
$X_{tts}, x_{tts,i}, c_{tts,i}$	Set, variables [MWh] and specific investment costs [M€/MWh] for the transport storage
$X_{wg}, x_{wg,i}, c_{wg,i}$	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the water supply technology
$X_{wt}, x_{wt,i}, c_{wt,i}$	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the waste treatment technology
$X_{wwt}, x_{wwt,i}, c_{wwt,i}$	Set, variables [MW] and specific investment costs [M€/MW] for the wastewater treatment technology
$X_{ws}, x_{ws,i}, c_{ws,i}$	Set, variables [tonne or m ³] and specific investment costs [M€/tonne or M€/m ³] for the water, waste and wastewater storage
$E_{pot,i}$	The maximum potential of i technology [MWh]

P_{max}	Maximum electrical load [MW]
L_h, L_c	Maximum heating and cooling load [MW]
D_t	Transport demand [MWh]
D_w	Water demand [m ³]
G_w	Waste generation [tonne]
G_{ww}	Wastewater generation [m ³]
m	Load factor

Appendix A

Table A1. Input data for Smart Islands method [35]

	Component	Indicator	$i_{x,y}$
Needs	Electricity	Electricity consumption [MWh per capita]	$i_{1,1}$
		Load factor	$i_{1,2}$
	Heat	Heating consumption [MWh per capita]	$i_{1,3}$
		HDD	$i_{1,4}$
	Cold	Cooling consumption [MWh per capita]	$i_{1,5}$
		CDD	$i_{1,6}$
	Waste treatment	Generated waste [tonne per capita]	$i_{1,7}$
		Separated waste [%]	$i_{1,8}$
	Wastewater treatment	Generated wastewater [m ³ per capita]	$i_{1,9}$
		Treated wastewater [%]	$i_{1,10}$
	Water	Water consumption [m ³ per capita]	$i_{1,11}$
	Transport	Transport energy consumption [MWh per capita]	$i_{1,12}$
Resources	Wind	Wind speed [m/s]	$i_{2,1}$
		Wind energy in total demand [%]	$i_{2,2}$
		Used wind potential [%]	$i_{2,3}$
	Solar	Solar irradiation [MWh/m ²]	$i_{2,4}$
		Solar energy in total demand [%]	$i_{2,5}$
		Used solar potential [%]	$i_{2,6}$
	Biomass	Biomass potential [MWh/m ²]	$i_{2,7}$
		Biomass energy in total demand [%]	$i_{2,8}$
		Used biomass potential [%]	$i_{2,9}$
	Hydro	Elevation [m]	$i_{2,10}$
		Hydro energy in total demand [%]	$i_{2,11}$
		Used hydro potential [%]	$i_{2,12}$
	Geothermal	Geothermal gradient [°C/100 m]	$i_{2,13}$
		Geothermal energy in total demand [%]	$i_{2,14}$
		Used geothermal potential [%]	$i_{2,15}$
Energy and telecommunication infrastructure	Grid infrastructure	Interconnection [MVA]	$i_{3,1}$
		Reserve [MVA]	$i_{3,2}$
		Variability factor	$i_{3,3}$
	Natural gas pipeline	Yes or No	$i_{3,4}$
	LNG terminal	Yes or No	$i_{3,5}$
	Oil terminal/refinery	Yes or No	$i_{3,6}$
	Oil derivatives terminal	Yes or No	$i_{3,7}$
	Telecommunications	Internet speed [Mbit/s]	$i_{3,8}$
		Mobile network coverage [%]	$i_{3,9}$
Water	Precipitation	Yearly precipitation	$i_{4,1}$
	Groundwater	Yes or No	$i_{4,2}$
	Water pipeline	Percentage of households [%]	$i_{4,3}$
	Desalination	Flow [m ³ /h]	$i_{4,4}$

Appendix B

Table B1. Energy carriers selection

Energy carriers	Energy carriers list
$if(i_{1,1} > 0)$	Electric energy
$if((i_{1,3} > 7) \text{ and } (i_{1,4} > 1500))$	District heating
$if((i_{1,5} > 7) \text{ and } (i_{1,6} > 1500))$	District cooling
$if(i_{1,12} > 10)$	Hydrogen
$if((i_{3,4} == 1) \text{ and } (i_{3,5} == 1))$	Natural gas
$If(((i_{2,7} > 200) \text{ and } (i_{2,8} < 0.3) \text{ and } (i_{2,9} < 0.3)) \text{ or } ((i_{1,7} > 7) \text{ and } (i_{1,8} < 0.5)) \text{ or } ((i_{1,9} > 7) \text{ and } (i_{1,10} < 0.5)) \text{ and } ((i_{3,6} == 1) \text{ or } (i_{3,7} == 1)))$	Biogas

Table B2. Technology selection for all sectors

Electric energy production technology	Electricity production technology list
$if((i_{1,1} > 7) \text{ and } (i_{1,2} > 0.2) \text{ and } (i_{2,1} > 7.5) \text{ and } (i_{2,2} < 0.3) \text{ and } (i_{2,3} < 0.5))$	Wind
$if((i_{1,1} > 1) \text{ and } (i_{1,2} > 0.1) \text{ and } (i_{2,4} > 1000) \text{ and } (i_{2,5} < 0.4) \text{ and } (i_{2,6} < 0.7))$	PV
$If((i_{1,1} > 9) \text{ and } (i_{1,2} > 0.1) \text{ and } (i_{2,4} > 1300) \text{ and } (i_{2,5} < 0.4) \text{ and } (i_{2,6} < 0.7))$	Solar
$If((i_{1,1} > 6) \text{ and } (i_{1,2} < 0.5) \text{ and } (i_{3,3} < 0.4) \text{ and } (i_{2,10} > 500) \text{ and } (i_{2,11} == 0) \text{ and } (i_{2,12} == 0))$	Hydro
$If((i_{1,1} > 4) \text{ and } (i_{2,7} > 150) \text{ and } (i_{2,8} < 0.5) \text{ and } (i_{2,9} < 0.5))$	Biomass
$If((i_{1,1} > 5) \text{ and } (i_{2,13} > 10) \text{ and } (i_{2,14} < 0.5) \text{ and } (i_{2,15} < 0.5))$	Geothermal
Heating production technology	Heating production technology list
$If((i_{1,3} > 1) \text{ and } (i_{2,4} > 1100) \text{ and } (i_{2,5} < 0.50) \text{ and } (i_{2,6} < 0.5))$	Solar collectors
$If((i_{1,3} > 2) \text{ and } \text{“Electric energy” in Energy carriers list})$	Heat pumps
$If(\text{“Geothermal” in Electricity production technology list})$	Geothermal
$If(\text{“Biomass” in Electricity production technology list})$	Biomass
Cooling production technology	Cooling production technology list
$if((i_{1,3} > 2) \text{ and } (i_{1,4} > 200) \text{ and } (i_{2,4} > 1300) \text{ and } (i_{2,5} < 0.50) \text{ and } (i_{2,6} < 0.5))$	Solar absorbers
$If(\text{“Heat pumps” in Heating production technology list})$	Heat pumps
$if((i_{1,3} > 1) \text{ and } (i_{1,4} > 200) \text{ and } \text{“Electricity” in Electricity carriers list})$	Electricity coolers
Transport technology	Transport technology list
$If((i_{1,12} > 6) \text{ and } \text{“Hydrogen” in Energy carriers list})$	Hydrogen
$If((i_{1,12} > 0.5) \text{ and } \text{“Electricity” in Energy carriers list})$	Electricity
$If((i_{1,12} > 6) \text{ and } \text{“Biogas” in energy carriers list})$	Biogas
Water technology	Water technology list
$If((i_{1,11} < 30) \text{ and } (i_{4,1} > 3000) \text{ and } (i_{4,3} == 0))$	Water collection
$if((i_{1,11} < 50) \text{ and } (i_{4,2} == 1))$	Water wells

<i>If</i> (($i_{4,2} == 0$) and ($i_{4,4} == 0$) (“Water collection” and “Water wells” not in Water technology list))	Desalination
Waste technology	Waste technology list
<i>If</i> (($i_{1,7} > 1.5$) and ($i_{1,8} < 0.4$))	Waste to Energy
Wastewater technology	Wastewater technology list
<i>If</i> (($i_{1,9} > 90$) and ($i_{1,10} < 0.4$))	Gasification

Table B3. Storage technology selection

Electricity storage	Electricity storage list
<i>If</i> (“Hydro” in Electricity production technology list)	Hydro
<i>if</i> (“Hydrogen” in Energy carriers list) and (“Hydro” not in Electricity production technology list) and (“PV” in Electricity production technology list) or (“Solar” in Electricity production technology list) or (“Wind” in Electricity production technology list))	Electrolyser + hydrogen
<i>if</i> (“Hydrogen” in Energy carriers list) and (“Hydro” not in Electricity production technology list) and (“Natural gas” or “Biogas”) in Energy carriers list)	Reformer + hydrogen
<i>if</i> (“Hydrogen” and “Hydro” not in Energy carriers list)	Battery
Thermal storage	Thermal storage list
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,3} > 5$))	Heat storage
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,5} > 7$))	Cold bank
Transport (fuel) storage	Transport storage list
<i>if</i> (“Hydrogen” in Transport technology list)	Hydrogen
<i>if</i> (“Biogas” in Transport technology list)	Biogas
Waste/wastewater storage	Waste/wastewater storage list
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,7} > 0$) and (“Waste to Energy” not in Waste technology list))	Waste fill
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,9} > 0$) and (“Gasification” not in Wastewater technology list))	Wastewater tanks

Table B4. Flow integration selection

Flow integration	Flow integration list
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,1} > 2$) and ($i_{1,3} > 2$) or (“Biomass” or “Solar” or “Geothermal” in Electricity production list))	CHP
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,1} > 2$) and ($i_{1,3} > 2$) and ($i_{1,5} > 2$) or (“Biomass” or “Solar” or “Geothermal” in Electricity production list))	Trigeneration
<i>if</i> (($i_{3,8} > 40$) and (“Desalination” in Water technology list))	Power and water
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,1} < 4$) and (“Waste to Energy” in Waste technology))	Heat and waste
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,1} == 4$) and (“Waste to Energy” in Waste technology))	Power and heat and waste
<i>if</i> (($i_{1,1} == 4$) and ($i_{1,5} > 5$) and (“Waste to Energy” in Waste technology list))	Power and heat and cold and waste
<i>If</i> (“Gasification” in Wastewater technology list)	Biogas and waste
<i>If</i> (“Wind” or “Solar” or “PV” in Electricity production technology list) and (“Hydrogen” in Energy carriers list))	Power and hydrogen
<i>if</i> (($i_{3,8} > 40$) and ($i_{3,9} > 0.5$) and (“Desalination” in Water technology list))	Power and transport

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